

Clerk to the Committee on Constitutional, Legal & Parliamentary Affairs,

Intelligent people who understand science know that sexual orientation and gender identity are not a choice and are a naturally diverse characteristic in animals, including in humans. The concept that humans are supposed to adhere exclusively to heterosexuality and gender norms is an unnatural invention of religion (especially colonial religions) and bigotry. This anti-LGBTQI bigotry is no more rational or based in science than racism. Both are merely inventions for oppression and not natural or based in science, and “treatment” for being LGBTQI is as unnecessary as treatment is for being Black.

The Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021 embarrasses Ghana on an international scale of civilization and modern society and will negatively affect its standing on the world stage. The United Nations has already declared that “Adopting the legislation in its current or any partial form would be tantamount to a violation of a number of human rights standards, including the absolute prohibition of torture.” This bill will only give the United Nations and wealthy nations reasons to decrease trade and travel (including for the Year of Return) with Ghana. It will discourage large companies, especially those headquartered in countries that value human rights, from expanding to Ghana, and it will harm all Ghanaians, even those who are not LGBTQI.

This legislation is going in wrong direction. Ghana already has colonial-era law that criminalizes homosexuality. If Ghana is going to become a leader in Africa and the world, it must repeal bigoted and primitive legislation like this, not add to it.

In order to solve our problems, we need to come together instead of making the same mistakes of adopting the bigotry and self-hatred that colonialism has imposed upon Ghana. We need to recognize that we are all human no matter our sexual orientation, and we share a culture and connection to each other through our ancestors and Africa. We need to recognize that LGBTQI people have always existed, and Ghana has always been a home to LGBTQI people. Driving LGBTQI people out of Ghana will do Ghana no more benefit today than colonialism and slavery did by forcing Africans from their homeland.

Signing this bill into law would not only violate agreements with the United Nations for human rights; it would violate Ghana’s own constitution. We call upon you and every member of parliament to vote no on this unconstitutional bill to deprive LGBTQI Ghanaians of their constitutional rights to equality. Thank you for your help.

T ■■■ L ■■■

■■■■@gmail.com